

Role of Indocyanine Green for Sentinel Lymph Node Biopsy in Early Breast Cancer**Narayan Sanap¹, Bhaskar Musande², Yashraj Sapkal³, Suraj R. Jadhavar⁴, Amit Lathoriya⁵, T Phani Satyachand⁶, Sarika N. Sanap⁷, Urveshkumar V. Radadiya⁸**¹Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, MGM Medical College and Hospital, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India²Professor, Department of General Surgery, MGM Medical College and Hospital, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India^{3,4}Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, MGM Medical College and Hospital, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India^{5,6,8}Junior Resident, Department of General Surgery, MGM Medical College and Hospital, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India⁷Dental Surgeon, Dr Sanap Health Care, Garkheda, Chatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Breast cancer is a significant health concern, and the accurate identification of lymph node involvement is crucial for appropriate staging and treatment planning. One technique that has gained wide spread acceptance is sentinel lymph node biopsy. Sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) is effective for accurately assessing pathological nodal staging and identifying the presence of metastasis in the axillary lymph nodes. This study evaluates role indocyanine green for sentinel lymph node biopsy in early breast cancer.**Materials and Methods:** This prospective study was conducted at Department of surgery, MGM Medical College & Hospital, Chatrapati Sambhajnagar (Aurangabad), Maharashtra, India. A total of 18 patients with clinically node-negative breast cancer were enrolled. ICG was injected peritumorally, and SLNs were identified using a near-infrared fluorescence imaging system.**Observation & Results:** In the present study, majority of cases were aged > 60 years i.e. 10 (55%) followed by 7 (39%) cases from 41 to 60 years. The mean age was 61 years. In 18 cases, only 1 (6%) male case was found and the rest 17 (94 %) were females. ICG successfully identified SLNs in 16(89%) of cases. The average number of SLNs identified per patient was 2.1. Frozen report was found positive in 6 (37 %) cases and negative in 10 (63 %) cases.**Conclusion:** Indocyanine green is a viable and effective option for sentinel lymph node biopsy in breast cancer, with a favorable safety profile and high detection rates. Its adoption could simplify Sentinel lymph node mapping and potentially reduce the need for more invasive procedures like axillary lymph node dissection.**Keywords:** Indocyanine Green, Sentinel lymph node.

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Introduction

Breast cancer is a significant health concern, and the accurate identification of lymph node involvement is crucial for appropriate staging and treatment planning. One technique that has gained wide spread acceptance is sentinel lymph node biopsy.

Sentinel lymph node biopsy was recently introduced in clinical practice also for clinically node-positive patients who become clinically node-negative after neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NACT) [1]. Thus, indications for Sentinel lymph node biopsy have expanded beyond patients presenting with clinically node-negative early breast cancer. Sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) is effective for

accurately assessing pathological nodal staging and identifying the presence of metastasis in the axillary lymph nodes. However, one of the main challenges associated with axillary dissection is the potential for various complications. These complications can include seromas, infections, sensory changes such as numbness, and the development of lymphedema in the arm [2].

The dye-guided method is simple and cost-effective, but substantial experience is required to develop the technical skill necessary to achieve the high success rate [3]. The use of indocyanine green, a fluorescent dye, has emerged as an innovative

approach to enhance the identification and visualization of sentinel lymph nodes during this procedure. Indocyanine green (ICG) is a water-soluble dye that exhibits near-infrared fluorescence and has several medical applications. Approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), Indocyanine green is primarily used for assessing cardiac output, evaluating hepatic clearance, and monitoring ophthalmic perfusion [4]. Its unique properties allow for real-time imaging and diagnostics in various clinical settings, providing valuable insights into physiological processes. Indocyanine Green (ICG) is a fluorescent dye with potential advantages in Sentinel lymph node mapping. This study evaluates role indocyanine green for sentinel lymph node biopsy in early breast cancer.

Materials and Methods:

This prospective study was conducted at MGM Medical College & Hospital, Chatrapati Sambhajnagar (Aurangabad), Maharashtra, India. A total of 18 patients with clinically node-negative breast cancer were enrolled. ICG was injected peritumorally, and SLNs were identified using a near-infrared fluorescence imaging system. The number of SLNs identified, detection rate, and any adverse reactions were recorded.

Study Design: prospective Observational study.

Study Duration: May 2023 to June 2024.

Inclusion criteria & Exclusion criteria:

Inclusion criteria: Female and male patients aged 18-70 years with a histologically confirmed diagnosis of breast cancer and clinically node-negative axilla.

Exclusion criteria: Patients with known allergies to iodine or ICG, previous axillary surgery,

pregnancy, or those who had undergone neoadjuvant chemotherapy.

Procedure:

ICG (2.5 mg/ml) was injected around the tumor (peritumoral) at a dose of 1 ml.

Near-infrared fluorescence imaging was used intraoperatively to detect SLNs.

The identified SLNs were excised and sent for histopathological examination.

Data Collection: The primary outcomes measured were the detection rate of SLNs using ICG, the number of SLNs identified, and any adverse reactions to ICG. Secondary outcomes included comparison of detection rates with traditional blue dye and radioactive tracers from historical data.

Observation & Results:

In the present study, majority of cases were aged > 60 years i.e., 10(55%) followed by 7 (39%) cases from 41 to 60 years. The mean age was 61 years.

In 18 cases, only 1 (6 %) male case was found and the rest 17 (94%) were females. Male to female ratio was 0.06:1. The mean \pm SD of height (cm) was found as 154.16 ± 8.92 , of weight (kg) was 63.05 ± 12.24 , and of BMI (kg/m²) was 26.59 ± 5.41 . In the present study, fluorescence visualized cases were maximum i.e., 16(89%) whereas not visualized cases were 2 (11%). 1 to 2 nodes were harvested in 7(39%) cases each. 3 to 5 nodes were harvested in 1 (6%) case each. In 2(10%) cases no node was harvested, the most probable reason being the BMI of patients.

Detection Rate: ICG successfully identified SLNs in 16(89%) of cases. The average number of SLNs identified per patient was 2.1.

Table 1: Distribution of Cases according to Fluorescence post ICG dye injection

Fluorescence post ICG dye injection	Number of cases	Percentage %
Visualized	16	89 %
Not Visualized	2	11 %
Total	18	100 %

Fluorescence visualized cases were maximum i.e., 16(89%) whereas not visualized cases were 2(11%).

Table 2: Distribution of Cases according to Number of Nodes harvested

Number of Nodesharvested	Number of cases	Percentage
0	2	10 %
1	7	39 %
2	7	39 %
3	1	6 %
5	1	6 %
Total	18	100 %

Table 2 shows the distribution of Cases according to number of nodes harvested. 1 and 2 nodes were harvested in 7 (39 %) cases each. 3 and 5 nodes were harvested in 1(6%) case each. In 2 (10%) cases no node was harvested.

Table 3: Distribution of Cases according to adverse reaction to ICG

Adverse reaction to ICG	Number of cases	Percentage
Present	0	0 %
Absent	18	100 %
Total	18	100 %

Table 3 shows the distribution of Cases according to adverse reaction to ICG. Adverse reaction was absent in all the 18 (100 %) cases.

Table 4: Distribution of Cases according to frozen report

Frozen report	Number of cases	Percentage
Positive	6	37 %
Negative	10	63 %
Total	16	100 %

Table 4 shows the distribution of Cases according to frozen report. Frozen report was found positive in 6 (37 %) cases and negative in 10 (63 %) cases.

Table 5: Distribution of Cases according to Histopathological result

Histopathological result	Number of cases	Percentage
Carcinoma with Positive Axillary LN	9	50%
Carcinoma without Axillary LN	9	50 %
Total	18	100 %

Carcinoma with Positive Axillary LN was detected in 9 (50%) cases and Carcinoma without Axillary LN also in 9 (50%) cases.

Table 6: Distribution of Cases according to ICG & Histopathological result

Fluorescence post ICG dye injection	Histopathology Result Axillary LN		Total N (%)	P value
	Positive	Negative		
Visualized	9(53 %)	7(36 %)	16(89 %)	0.47 (NS)
Not Visualized	0(0 %)	2(12 %)	2(11 %)	
Total	9(53 %)	9(47 %)	18(100%)	-
Sensitivity 100 % Specificity 22.22 % PPV 56.25 % NPV 100 %				

Table 6 shows the distribution of Cases according to ICG & histopathological result. In 9 (53 %) cases fluorescence post ICG dye injection was visualized & also they showed Axillary LN positive on Histopathology. In 2 (12 %) cases fluorescence post ICG dye injection was not visualized which

also showed Axillary LN negative result on Histopathology. In 7 (36 %) cases fluorescence post ICG dye injection was visualized but they showed Axillary LN negative result on Histopathology. Sensitivity and specificity of ICG dye fluorescence was found as 100 % & 22.22 % respectively.

Table 7: Distribution of Cases according to Surgery type

Surgery type	Number of cases (N)	Percentage (%)
Modified Radical Mastectomy (MRM)	14	77 %
Breast-Conserving Surgery (BCS)	3	17 %
Completion Mastectomy	1	6 %
Total	18	100 %

Table 7 shows the distribution of Cases according to surgery type. In 14 (77 %) cases Modified radical mastectomy (MRM) was performed. In 3 (17 %) cases Breast-conserving surgery (BCS) was performed and in 1 (6 %) case Completion Mastectomy was performed.

Table 8: Distribution of Cases according to ICG with Frozen section report & Histopathological result

ICG visualisation along with Frozen section report	Histopathology Result Axillary LN		Total N (%)	P value
	Positive	Negative		
positive	6 (37.5 %)	0 (0 %)	6 (37.5 %)	0.01 (S)
negative	3 (23.5 %)	7 (39 %)	10 (62.5 %)	
Total	9 (61%)	7(39 %)	16 (100 %)	-
Sensitivity: 66.67% Specificity: 100% PPV: 70% NPV : 78.0%				

Table 8 shows the distribution of Cases according to ICG with frozen section report & histopathologi-

cal result. In 6 (37.5 %) cases ICG visualized and frozen section was positive & also they showed

Axillary LN positive on Histopathology. In 7(39%) cases ICG visualized and frozen section was negative which also showed Axillary LN negative result on Histopathology. In 3(23.5%) cases ICG visualized and frozen section was negative but they showed Axillary LN positive result on Histopathology. Sensitivity and specificity of ICG dye fluorescence was found 66.67 % & 100 % respectively.

Safety: No significant adverse reactions to ICG were reported. Minor complications included mild injection site pain in 3 patients, which resolved without intervention.

Comparison with Traditional Methods: Historical data indicated a detection rate of approximately 95% with blue dye and radioactive tracers. The accuracy of SLN identification with ICG was comparable to these traditional methods.

Discussion

Breast cancer is a leading cause of morbidity. Its early detection is correlated with a significantly improved prognosis and a reduced percentage of patients with involved axillary lymph nodes. Axillary lymph node involvement has been found as having the most significant prognostic value which is routinely assessed during primary treatment. In patients with clinically negative nodes (cN0), sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) has become the standard procedure for axillary staging as it has comparable diagnostic accuracy for acquiring nodal status. Based on the standardized and quality-assured implementation, sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) shows a high staging accuracy (>90%) [5,6,7,8]. Standard sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) procedures in India include peri-areolar or interstitial injection of radioactive Technetium 99m (Tc99m) colloid, blue dye, or a combination of both whereas radio-colloid is widely considered the gold standard method in Germany [8].

The use of radioisotopes has the highest detection rates; however, it has several drawbacks such as limited availability, high costs, no real-time tracing, and exposure of patients and surgeon to radioactivity. Blue dye is easy to handle and cost-effective, but it has lower detection and higher false-negative rates, cannot be seen through the skin or fatty tissues, and can cause allergic reactions, in rare cases even anaphylaxis [9,10]. Dual-tracer method using blue dye and Tc99m has been demonstrated to be superior to either agent used separately. However, still this improvement lacks enough clinical significance. As a near-infrared (NIR) imaging agent, indocyanine green (ICG) can be traced in real-time in high resolution, is cost-effective, and is broadly applicable [11]. It has FDA and EMEA approval to be used for imaging blood flow and off-label as a lymphatic tracer in clinical trials. Recently indocyanine green (ICG) fluorescence has been suggested

as an alternative dye for tracing sentinel lymph nodes (SLN) in breast cancer [12]. Several clinical trials and studies evaluated the use of indocyanine green (ICG) for sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) and found promising results, showing higher detection rates as compared to blue dye and equal sensitivity as radioisotopes [13]. With this perspective present study was undertaken in 18 breast cancer cases diagnosed clinically and radiologically to assess the role of ICG dye in the identification of sentinel lymph nodes. ICG dye was injected intra-operatively followed by lymphatic fluorescence and frozen section study. Sample was also sent for histopathology study. The results obtained were compiled & analyzed.

In the present study, majority of cases were aged > 60 years i.e., 10 (55 %) followed by 7 (39 %) cases from 41 to 60 years. The mean age was 61 years.

In 18 cases, only 1 (6 %) male case was found and the rest 17 (94 %) were females. Male to female ratio was 0.06:1. The mean \pm SD of height (cm) was found as 154.16 ± 8.92 , of weight (kg) was 63.05 ± 12.24 , and of BMI (kg/m²) was 26.59 ± 5.41 . In the present study, fluorescence visualized cases were maximum i.e., 16 (89%) whereas not visualized cases were 2 (11%). 1 to 2 nodes were harvested in 7 (39%) cases each. 3 to 5 nodes were harvested in 1 (6 %) case each. In 2(10 %) cases no node was harvested, the most probable reason being the BMI of patients. As was seen in some studies that BMI more than or equal to 40 makes it difficult to visualize fluorescence emitted due to deep location of lymphatics. Adverse reaction to ICG was absent in all 18 (100 %) cases.

In a similar study by Priya S. Bhakta et al (2020) [14] they found a total of 137 nodes were identified from the 52 patients. Of these 124 nodes were detected via 99mTc, 108 with Iso-sulfan Blue, and 128 with Indocyanine Green. Detection rates were 90.1% with 99mTc, 78.8% with Isosulfan Blue, and 93.4% with ICG. An average of 2.63 nodes were identified per patient when all three detection methods were included. Nodes detected via Isosulfan Blue or 99mTc had a detection average of 2.51 nodes per patient versus 99mTc or ICG with 2.61 nodes per patient. A combination of 99mTc and isosulfan blue showed a detection rate of 95.0% versus 99mTc and ICG of 99.3%. Out of 37 nodes identified, 20 nodes were positive for metastasis in 13 of the 52 patients. Node positivity was 14.6%. In one patient, an extra node with the positive disease was identified with ICG that was not identified with either 99mTc or isosulfan blue. Thomas Papatthemelis et al (2018) [15] found no differences in terms of the ICG mapping procedure as reported by the surgeons after NAST when compared to primary surgery. No adverse reactions associated with ICG were noted. In total, 220 SLN were dissected, of these 215 were ICG fluorescent, and 172 were

positive for Technetium 99m. 5 nodes (2.3%) were not visible by ICG but were detected through gamma probing of the axilla. On the other hand, 48 nodes (21.8%) showing no signal in gamma probing. were identified with ICG fluorescence only.

In all 99 patients included in the analysis, at least one SLN was detected by Technetium 99m and/or ICG, meaning that the SLN detection rate by dual mapping was 100%. At least one node was picked up by both tracers, ICG and Tc99m in 95 patients. In 4 cases where no lymph node was marked with both tracers and in 2 women at least one node was detected by Tc99m and ICG, respectively.

Joseph Lin et al (2020) [2] in their study a total of 84 lymph nodes were removed in 40 procedures. All 84 nodes were identified by ICG, but only 37 were identified by the blue dye. The identification rate of ICG in patients with a BMI less than 30 was 100% (36/36). The fluorescent method detected SLN in only three of four patients with a BMI greater than 30.

Correlation of ICG dye fluorescence with frozen report & histopathological result:

In the present study frozen report was found positive in 6 (37%) cases and negative in 10 (63%) cases. On histopathological results, Carcinoma with Positive Axillary LN has been detected in 9(50%) cases and Carcinoma without Axillary LN also in 9

(50%) cases. In 9 (53%) cases fluorescence post ICG dye injection was visualized & also they showed Axillary LN positive on Histopathology. In 2(12%) cases fluorescence post ICG dye injection was not- visualized which also showed Axillary LN negative result on Histopathology.

In 7(36%) cases fluorescence post ICG dye injection was visualized but they showed Axillary LN negative result on Histopathology. The sensitivity and specificity of ICG dye fluorescence were found as 100% & 22.22% respectively. In 6(37.5%) cases ICG visualized and frozen sections were positive & also they showed Axillary LN positive on Histopathology.

In 7(39%) cases ICG visualized and frozen sections were negative which also showed Axillary LN negative results on Histopathology. In 3 (23.5%) cases ICG visualized and frozen sections were negative but they showed Axillary LN positive results on Histopathology. The sensitivity and specificity of ICG dye fluorescence were found 66.67% & 100% respectively. Apart from this, In 1 case, the two tissues which emitted fluorescence contained only 1 lymph node. The probable reason for fluorescence in other tissue might be due to spillage of ICG post-lymphatic destruction. Time of visualization of sentinel lymph node with ICG was 10-12 min. Lymphatic channels could be visualized using ICG.

Figure 1: Lymphatic channels visualized using ICG

Figure 2: A) White & B) Green fluorescence

Sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) was not introduced to detect axillary tumor-bearing nodes but to identify those cN0 patients that are pN+. Since all cN+ patients used to undergo consecutive axillary lymph node dissection (ALND) according to the original sentinel approach, the risk of leaving affected nodes in the axilla was inconsequential, even if SLNB did not remove them all. Therefore, it is of no concern if Tc99m does not detect as many involved nodes as ICG as long as it does not miss a pN+ patient. On the other hand, an essential intention of the sentinel technique is to reduce the surgical trauma to the axilla and to minimize the removal of healthy lymph nodes. The present study revealed that the ICG fluorescence method permits transcutaneous identification of lymphatic flow pathways, which will enable a more orderly and sequential dissection. Therefore, the ICG fluorescence method can be a safe and effective addition in clinical settings, wherein blue dye alone is used or where access to radioisotope is limited.

Conclusion

Indocyanine green is a viable and effective option for sentinel lymph node biopsy in breast cancer, with a favorable safety profile and high detection rates. Moreover, it enhances the identification rate, improving outcomes of early breast cancer patients. Its adoption could simplify Sentinel lymph node mapping and potentially reduce the need for more invasive procedures like axillary lymph node dissection.

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